

**TEACHERS' INNOVATIVENESS AND ADOPTION OF SCHOOL
INNOVATIONS IN BARRA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL,
DIVISION OF MISAMIS ORIENTAL**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 2

Pages: 250-255

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2956

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14729633

Manuscript Accepted: 12-19-2024

Teachers' Innovativeness and Adoption of School Innovations in Barra Elementary School, Division of Misamis Oriental

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the influence of the adoption of school innovation to teachers' innovativeness. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to determine the extent of teachers' innovativeness. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the teachers' innovativeness and the level of adoption of school innovation and Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of adoption of school innovation and teachers' innovativeness. Findings revealed that teachers were "most of the time" innovative and the level of adoption of school innovation was high. Additionally, it was found out that teachers' innovativeness was influenced by the level of adoption of the school innovation. As a summary, it was recommended that school principal or school head should continue to inspire teachers to be more innovative and teachers to use their creativity and innovativeness. The teachers to remain steadfast in their quest to provide more engaging and motivating learning activities.

Keywords: *teachers' innovativeness, adoption of school innovation, radio-based instruction, audio-video instruction*

Introduction

Education calls for the dynamic and innovative teachers who can transcend learning beyond the four confines of the classroom to make learning more meaningful and contribute to the holistic development of the learners to become for productive citizens in their local communities.

The framework of this study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to RA 9155 also known as Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, this policy aims to strengthen the school-based management by further devolving the governance of education to schools, expanding community participation and involvement, and making the delivery of education services to the learners more responsive, efficient, and effective through an enhanced school planning and improvement that lays down specific interventions through initiated projects in schools.

In consonance with this act, all teaching and non-teaching personnel are encouraged to create, innovate school-based initiated projects geared towards the improvement of teaching-learning process and school governance. Additionally, in the 21st century education, the educational system should empower learners with skills and competences to cope with a constantly changing landscape.

Innovation is the introduction of new ideas, goods, services, and practices which are intended to be useful. Further, it was accentuated by Gurin, et al (2019) that all teaching personnel are enjoined by the Department of Education (DepEd) to make an innovation that produces innovative ideas about using technology and innovations in the teaching-learning process; project that will help advance knowledge on using technology to support student learning; projects that help advance knowledge about using the technology to support student learning; and, project-based classroom rather than book-based instruction.

Reference is often made to skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, collaborative skills, innovation, digital literacy, and adaptability. What is negotiable is how best to achieve the development of those skills, in particular which teaching and learning approaches are suitable for facilitating or enabling complex skills development

Subsequently, Tan (2018) espoused that innovative in education is conducted or made to address gaps on access, quality and relevance and governance and/management of education services such as; increase enrolment/participation rate, reduce/zeroing-in-drop-out rate, and reduce failure rate; improve academic performance; enhance learning environment/improve physical facilities; and, product of contextualization and indigenization.

Gutierrez (2018) claimed that the Philippine government's vision for the future of education is to embrace and development of 21st century skills and other essential learner qualities as the acquisition of skills to embrace complex challenges and the development of the person as a whole, valuing common prosperity, sustainability and well-being. Further, it was stressed out that well-being is related to equitable access to quality of life, including health, civic engagement, social connections, education, security, life satisfaction and the environment.

In a similar investigation, Siaotong & Lariosa (2019) accentuated that teacher's education, trainings, experience and personal characteristics are of prime importance in bringing out the desired changes in the educational system. It is the teacher who will give meaning and life to any educational program. State of the art facilities will redound to oblivion if the teacher will not give life to it. The far reaching influence of teachers accord as an agent of change in society is beyond question. The emergence of new program designs

and technologies increased the need for qualified teachers. Innovative teachers are needed to put into practice educational ideas which are meaningful and worthwhile.

With this end in view, the teachers' behavior is equally an important issue in the teaching learning process. Teachers who wish pupils to learn at the maximum level should do their best to discover and integrate innovative ways of teaching. They need to take a quantum leap in teaching approaches, methods and technology and be mindful of the fast changes in the educational system.

In the Philippines, classes are heterogeneous where students have diverse social and economic backgrounds, exposures, and experiences. To facilitate learning students with personal differences under the same classroom, teachers need to adopt and use of innovative teaching approaches and strategies to respond to students' diversity and learning needs. The research is based on the assumption that innovative teaching has a positive impact on the performance of students' diversity.

It is based on this context the researcher has decided to conduct an investigation on the extent of teachers' innovativeness and the level of adoption of school innovations in Barra Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

The study aimed to ascertain the extent of teachers' innovativeness and the level of adoption of school innovations in Barra Elementary School in the Division of Misamis Oriental. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the extent of teachers' innovativeness in teaching in Barra Elementary School in the Division of Misamis Oriental?
2. What is the level of adoption of school innovations in Barra Elementary School when categorized as:
 - 2.1. Very High
 - 2.2. High
 - 2.3. Moderate
 - 2.4. Low
 - 2.5. Very Low
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of adoption of school innovations and the extent of teachers' innovativeness in Barra Elementary School?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It was employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations. In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design will be utilized to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis will be based on generated information from statistical tools. This method was also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the public elementary school teachers of Barra Elementary School in the Division of Misamis Oriental. There were thirty (30) teacher-respondents who answered the survey questionnaire on teachers' innovativeness and the level of adoption of school innovations in Barra Elementary School for the school year 2023 -2024. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The research instruments utilized in this study was adapted from Gurin, et al (2019) who espoused that teachers' innovativeness is needed to put into practice the educational ideas which are meaningful, sensible, and use of innovative strategies to respond to students' diversity.

The research instruments composed of two parts. Part 1 is on the teachers' innovativeness in teaching-learning approaches and strategies with ten (10) indicators. Subsequently, Part 2 of the survey questionnaire is on the level of adoption of school innovation which were composed of ten (10) indicators and described and categorized as; very high, high, moderate, low, very low.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and School Principal to conduct the study.

Subsequently, the same approval was sought from the teacher-respondents to allow the researcher gather the needed data on their innovativeness and the level of adoption and utilization of innovative teaching and learning approaches and strategies for the school year 2023-2024.

After the respondents provided the information, the researcher immediately retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted to the Statistician for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatments were utilized to analyse the data of the study:

Problem 1. Mean values and standard deviation will be used to present the extent of teachers' innovativeness.

Problem 2. Mean values and standard deviation will be used to present the level of adoption of school innovations.

Problem 3. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation will be utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of adoption of school innovations and the extent of teachers' innovativeness.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the finding resulting from the study on teachers' innovativeness and adoption of school innovations. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the extent of teachers' innovativeness in teaching in Barra Elementary School in the Division of Misamis Oriental?

Teachers' ability to utilize new teaching approaches and strategies may help improve teaching-learning and the academic outcomes of learners as well as address real learning challenges which also facilitate the promotion of equitable learning.

Teachers' innovativeness in teaching help encourage learners' creativity and innovation by stimulating learners to present different ideas, solve problems in their own ways, and use their imaginativeness. Additionally, it was emphasized that innovative teaching can help to build better relationships between teachers and learners and among learners with varied learning interests.

Table 1 presents the extent of teachers' innovativeness in teaching in Barra Elementary School.

Table 1. Mean Distribution of Teachers' Innovativeness in Teaching

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Develops radio-based instruction	4.90	.305	Always
2. Develops audio-video based instruction.	4.76	.430	Always
3. Develops learning activity sheets	4.46	.571	Always
4. Develops contextualized home learning modules.	4.30	.651	Always
5. Designs synchronous learning tools.	4.16	.647	Most of the Time
6. Designs asynchronous learning tools.	4.03	.731	Most of the Time
7. Designs offline learning tools	3.76	.727	Most of the Time
8. Designs online learning tools.	3.66	.758	Most of the Time
9. Designs and Utilizes Google classroom	3.33	.884	Sometimes
10. Designs learning activities using Microsoft 365.	3.06	.868	Sometimes
Overall Mean	4.04	.657	Most of the time

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/1.81-2.60 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1 displays the mean distribution of teachers' innovativeness in teaching. Overall, the respondents rated the teachers' innovativeness as "most of the time" with a mean of 4.04 (SD = .657). This result implies that teachers were most of the time utilized innovative teaching strategies to enhance and stimulate learners' participation and improve performance.

The indicator which states that "develops radio-based instruction" obtained the highest mean of 4.90 (SD= .305) which is verbally described as "Always". The result indicates that teachers continuously innovative their teaching in order to intensify learners' participation and involvement in learning which is indicative of their motivation to develop radio-based instruction. It can be deduced based on finding that learners are more stimulated to learn in radio-based instruction than the traditional lecture demonstration approach.

Paras, et al (2021) argued that teachers' utilization of innovative instructional activities create an atmosphere where learners are interested to engage and participate in different learning situations which also help them benefits from an inspiring learning activities designed by teachers in exercise of their innovative teaching activities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.06 (SD = .868) is verbally described as "sometimes" in the indicator "Designs learning activities using Microsoft 365". The result implies that teachers occasionally utilized Microsoft 365 in designing instructional activities which help promote learning.

Casas (2021) asserted that teachers are confronted with an array of innovative approaches and strategies in teaching and they can decide

what particular innovative strategy is best for their learners. It was also emphasized that teachers’ ability to provide learning materials help facilitate learners’ learning interest and mastery.

Problem 2. What is the level of adoption of school innovations in Barra Elementary School when categorized as: Very High, High, Moderate, Low, and Very Low?

The level of learners’ adoption to teachers’ innovativeness in teaching may vary as to whether they are very high, high, moderate, low, and very low. Table 2 presents the mean distribution of the level of adoption of school innovation.

Table 2. Mean Distribution on the Level of adoption of School Innovation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Adopts and implements radio-based learning.	4.68	.345	Very High
2. Adopts and implements audio-video based learning	4.66	.479	Very High
3. Adopts and implements learning activity sheets.	4.46	.571	Very High
4. Adopts and implements contextualized learning modules.	4.33	.660	Very High
5. Adopts and implements synchronous learning.	4.16	.698	High
6. Adopts and implements asynchronous learning.	4.00	.742	High
7. Adopts and implements offline learning.	3.76	.773	High
8. Adopts and implements online learning.	3.66	.711	High
9. Adopts and implements Google classroom.	3.30	.915	Moderate
10. Adopts and implements Microsoft 365.	3.20	.961	Moderate
Overall Mean	4.02	.686	High

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High/3.41-4.20 High/2.61-3.40 Moderate/1.81-2.60 Low/1.00-1.80 Very Low

Table 2 displays the mean distribution on the level of adoption of school innovation. Overall, the respondents rated the adoption of school innovation as “High” as manifested with a mean of 4.02 (SD = .686). This result implies that innovation was highly adopted by teachers in Barra Elementary School. It can be deduced based on findings that the school has highly adopted and implemented innovative teaching. Thus, it encourages teachers to adopt and implement innovative teaching approaches and strategies such as the use of radio-based and the audio-video instructional technology to improve learning.

The indicator which states that the school “Adopts and implements radio-based learning” obtained the highest mean of 4.68 (SD= .345) which is verbally described as “Very High”. The result indicates that radio-based instruction were highly adopted by Barra Elementary School. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers are encouraged to utilize the radio-based instruction in their classes.

Paras, et al (2021) avowed that the level of adoption of school innovation such as the use of radio-based instruction provides opportunities for learners to learn while they are in their respective homes through the use of their radio-audio lectures and discussion.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.20 (SD = .961) is verbally described as “Moderate” in the indicator “Adopts and implements Microsoft 365”. This implies that the use of Microsoft 365 is adopted and implemented judiciously and unassumingly is school.

Martinez (2022) affirmed that less effective innovative approach and teaching strategies are moderately adopted and implemented by school which means that the school only adopts and implements innovation that stimulates learning and students’ participation and engagements in learning activities to improve achievements and school performance.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of adoption of school innovations and the extent of teachers’ innovativeness in Barra Elementary School?

The level of adoption of school innovation is said to influence learning and learners’ academic and school performance. The adoption of innovation motivates learners to learn and helps teachers to create an inspiring, motivating, and engaging learning environment and experiences to students.

Table 3 presents the relationship between the level of adoption of school innovations and the extent of teachers’ innovativeness.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Level of Adoption of School Innovation and the Extent of Teachers’ Innovativeness

Innovation	Teachers’ Innovativeness			
	r	P-Value	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Adoption of School Innovation	.934	.000	Very High Relationship	Rejected

*significant at p<0.05 alpha level

Table 3 displays the results of the test of significant relationship between the level of adoption of school innovation and teachers’ innovativeness. Results revealed that the adoption of school innovation has very high relationship to teachers’ innovativeness as evident by the r value of .934 which is higher than the P-value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This result implies that teachers’ innovativeness is greatly influenced by the level of adoption of school innovation. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers are more innovative if the school leaders encouraged them to use their creativity and innovativeness.

This finding was supported by Paras, et al (2021) who avowed that school who adopts and implements innovation encourages teachers to use their creativity, initiative, and innovativeness. Additionally, it was emphasized that school leaders who adopt innovation in school encourage teachers to be innovative and creative in their teaching.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Teachers are innovative and creative in their teaching. They can use their creativity and innovativeness to design teaching-learning activities that are stimulating to learners in order to enhance engagement and participation to learning tasks vis-à-vis to improve learning and school performance.

In addition, the school leaders who adopt and implement innovation encourage teachers to use their creativity and imitativeness to design innovative learning approaches and strategies which are stimulating and inspiring to learners. Learners who are stimulated and motivated enhance engagement and participation in learning activities.

Successively, teachers' motivation and commitment in teaching coupled with the school leaders' support and adoption to innovation inspire teachers to innovate as well as revolutionize or design approaches and strategies in order to make learning more meaningful and informative to learners.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

The School Principal and School heads are encouraged to inspire teachers to be more innovative in their teaching especially in designing and implementing teaching technology to intensify learning.

Teachers are also encouraged to remain steadfast in their quest to provide the more engaging and motivating learning activities and inspire them to enhance their constructive learning interest.

Parents are also encouraged to provide the appropriate home-support to their children to develop positive attitude in adopting innovative teaching and learning activities in school.

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